

Integrating Nature and Gender: A Study of Indian Environmental Movements

Anuja Gupta

Abstract: *The paper explores the structural intersection of environment, gender, caste, and land rights within Indian environmental and social movements. Unlike Western ideological feminism, Indian ecofeminism emerges from grassroots struggles for basic livelihood, water, and survival. Historical systems like feudalism, patriarchal texts, and colonial/post-colonial land ownership patterns traditionally denied women material resources and land rights. However, through the contributions of activists like Kamla Bhasin, Bina Agarwal, and Sushma Iyengar, along with landmark struggles like the Chipko movement, the Bodhgaya Land Movement, and the Telangana peasant revolt, women successfully transitioned from passive victims of environmental degradation to active agents of change. By reclaiming spaces in public domains, courts, and agricultural practices (such as ploughing), lower-caste and marginalized women effectively challenged both patriarchal control and Brahminical caste hierarchies to demand social justice and sustainable development.*

Keywords: *Ecofeminism, Land rights, Environmental movements, Caste hierarchy, Women's agency.*

Introduction:

India has had stories of movements, protests, livelihood, status, land acquisition and compensation after land acquisition. The paper analyses the relationship between land and feminist movement in India from a sociological viewpoint. Feminist movement in India rose out of the desire to protect themselves from the intense harsh environmental conditions to which they were subjected and had to deal with the harsh reality to fend for themselves. The paper examines the role of two prominent feminist Kamla Bhasin and Sushma Iyengar who had pioneered women's movement in India from a developmental perspective. Feminism in India was not based on any ideological struggle as reflected in the western countries. These development activists analyse how the demand for basic right like demand for water and safe livelihood becomes a central piece in their struggle for their women's rights. The paper examines how their victimhood is transferred to an active agency in which they strive to survive and assert their livelihood.

Theoretical connection between land and women:

The relationship between land, caste and gender were much influenced by cultural practices, modes of production. Women's exclusion from the land rights was motivated by the concept that women's reproductive rights should be controlled and her sexuality should be under a male's gaze. Ancient Hindu texts like Manusmritis where the Brahmins were allotted reading and teaching the sacred texts, while the labouring community were the sudras who formed the bulk of the population, gradually the labouring class became the dominant caste (Omvedt, 2011). Further in pre- Independent India, the kings transferred the temple property in the of the Brahmins, who controlled them and had sole autonomy over the land and established their supremacy (Habib, 2002). Feudalism was established from above when the king allotted lands and their control to the feudal lords who controlled those who would work on their land (Kosambi, 1965). Jagirdars were established by the Mughal rulers, who gifted them a tract of land, whose tax was to be collected by the jagirdar, he would keep a small portion of amount, his salary

under him and would transfer the rest of the fund to the King. These historical factors made the man, the sole owner and controller of the land. After independence, there was a fear that the control of land in the hands of the women would make the men susceptible at the hands of the men, who would now be vulnerable (Chaudhuri, 1993)

Women have traditionally been denied right to land according to the Mitakshara school of law.

Women have been closely associated with nature. Ortner (1972) had conceptualised how women and nature were closely related while Shiva (2014) examines how violence against women is violence against nature itself. Environmental exploitation is an inseparable aspect of patriarchal world that is connected with capitalist and developmental perspective. Women become the centre of existence in these issues as they are the storehouse of knowledge linking food, fodder, water, manure, herbs with their daily existence. Their question also brings to the fore that when men leave their villages and migrate to newer areas, women are all left alone to take care of their children and themselves. Bina Agarwal (2002). In India case studies and real activist work by Bina Agarwal, Kamala Bhasin, Sushma Iyengar has pointed to the intrinsic connection between land, women and caste.

Indian environmental movement was largely influenced by the teachings of Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi. His ideas on satyagraha and self reliance were appreciated and applied in the environmental movements initiated by Sundarlal Bahuguna and Chandni Prasad Bhatt. They are credited with the initiation of the DGSM or Dashauli Gram Swarajya Mandal or the tree hugging movement commonly known as Chipko movement. Gandhiji's emphasis on civilisation, anti-machinery, useless modernisation and commercialisation were great impetus for the environmentalists. He emphasised on developing the villages and let it flourish as a unit which was contrary to the western notion of machinery, civilisation and modernisation (Curzon, 1998).

Case Studies:

Kamala Bhasin upon her return from Germany in development sociology joined the Udaipur voluntary based organisation called the Seva Mandir, whose main aim was to mobilise the people to reach their own development. So, the organisation first began to educate the people and make them literate. But after a few exercises, she realised the futility of the activity, it then occurred to her that in a place where people were dying of thirst literacy held no meaning for them. Slowly, she also realised that slogans and folk songs were the only tools available to educate the women. Her work in India began in the 80s. At a time when mobile phones were unavailable, she spread her ideas through posters and wall motifs with slogans like "*Mein parna chahti hu*" that translates to: "I want to read". Kamla Bhasin not only strove for women's literacy but also worked for their overall development, providing them with agency and making their voices vocal. In 1992, a woman from Rajasthan Bhanwari Devi who worked for the Rajasthan government's Women's Development Programme was brutally raped. Women organised in groups and under the guidance of Kamla Bhasin, they organised mass protests that resulted in the Vishakha guidelines of 1997.

Bina Agarwal discovers that caste and influence (pairavi) were the two most important social capital in Bihar. A person's caste and heritage determined how the interaction with her or them should be. There have been books and scholarly books written on landless women (Kelkar, 1991). The Bodhgaya Land Movement

from 1978- 88. (Prasad, 2005). The method used by BLBM fought on multiple fronts – it was first the women’s fight to organise their right to own land. Secondly, it was also a fight against caste hierarchy. Ploughing the land was a dual struggle against both the Brahmanism and gendered patriarchal notion, because land is culturally seen as a woman and plough was the male, who alone has the right to control the land, hence allowing women to plough the land was a blow both the gendered control of the land and on the caste concept that only the Brahmins have the right to control the land. Focusing on this Sharmila Rege (1998) and Chhaya Datar (1999) have argued that caste oppression begins as soon as women are denied of material resources.

Sushma Iyengar, founder of Kutch Mahila Vikas Sangathan organised women committee to facilitate a space where women would be consciousness of the disadvantages that they were facing and organisations like Jagori and Saheli and SEWA training women to form organisations that would empower their community, create the craft items and sell it in the market rather than selling it through middle agents. Kutch also faced lack of water supplies that made their conditions quite deplorable, as men would leave their village and women had to travel long distances to bring water for consumption and domestic use. Kutch Mahila Vikas was also successful in creating a women’s space where they could meet, talk, laugh and spend the time as they liked. It was one of the court cases that made the KMV more successful. There was a report where the women wanted to till the land next to their village with the vision that the dry land could be used for harvesting rainfall. However, the male came in drastically against the women taking control of the land, they said that the women were not allowed to till land, the men started a court case which brought the women from their private spaces to the public domain of the court. Hence, the same mechanism that made women victims also empowered them and gave them agency.

Conclusion:

Bridging environmental and women’s movement

Depletion of natural resources have been one of the major reasons for women to rise in revolt and protest. Depleting environmental resources affects women from the marginal section to a larger degree because due to the varying reasons of stratification of the society, it’s the women who are depended on the natural environment for their food, fodder, water and fuel. Remarkably, some of the major environmental issues have been transformed into feminist movement. The Chipko for instance was fuelled by the prevalent ideology that the forests of the Tehri Garhwal district purified water, air, soil and all basis of human life. The women in those areas, tied sacred thread around the trees in protest of the rampant deforestation. Women actively participated in the Chipko movement because it was their responsibility to collect food and food for their family members and domestic animals. In addition to the domestic role played by women, the Tehri Garhwal area was poverty ridden area, where the annual per capital income was only 129 Rs, given the amount of such money, it was irresistible for women who willingly participated in the movement. Women blocked roads and prevented bulldozers from cutting the trees. The word Chipko, same from the word *chupak* or hung and attributed to women hugging around the tree trunks.

In Telangana too, land and women’s movement arose together. The peasants in Telangana were deprived they were taxed heavily and sometimes the land of the peasants were transferred to the landlord’s name without any protest. One member

from each peasant family was sent to the landlords and made to carry pots, or collect fodder and supply agricultural implements freely to the landlords. Girls of the peasants were kept in the house of the landlords and when the landlord's daughter got married the peasant's daughter was sent along as a concubine (Suguna,2009). In 1949, peasants rose in revolt against the Deshmukhs, Suryapet, and women participated in large number in this protest. They rose against mass poverty and feudal exploitation. Andhra Vanitha an organisation of the women was formed where they campaigned against child marriage for widow remarriage and for increasing the minimum wages. Women participated in such struggles because in large parts they were the tobacco leaf collectors, worked as agricultural workers. So while the lower caste and class women faced the burden of extreme poverty, rape and insult, the upper class faced social segregation, purdah was practised, education was denied to them, early marriage and widow marriage was denied. Telangana was ruled by the Nizam, dominated by the Muslim culture, women were denied public participation. When the communist movement began with the entry of the Andhra Maha Sabha, women plunge into the protest along with men, they revolted against feudal landlords, they came out to the call for changing the social structure.

Interface between political personal and public became clear. An incident recounts on how a woman was prevented by her elder brother on marrying an old already married man, the examples also recite the tales of how men encouraged their women family member to say no. When the Telangana land struggle started, the torchbearers of the struggle wanted women to leave home and participate in the struggle. Along with landlessness, increasing taxes, low wages, issues like wife beating, child hygiene. The Navjivan Mahila Mandal started organising protests and bring to fore the greater women's interests so that women and the society at large would grow awareness about the subordinate condition of the women. In Telangana began the Srikakulam movement

Thus, we see that environmental movement in India differed from the West because, it was a movement for the restoration of social justice. Ramchandra Guha had mentioned three categories of people, the omnivores those who exploits the natural resources, the ecological refugee who are displaced due to the environmental degradation and cutting of the trees and the ecosystem people who are dependent upon the natural resources for their livelihood. Initially in the 19th century the men were the forerunner in the movement, but in the 20th century, the women became the forerunner and arranged for the organisation of the environmental movement.

So contemporary women's movement was also a movement for cleaning the society of its ills and of protecting the environment. Bina Agarwal also writes that the spontaneous participation of women in environmental issue, springs from her assigned gender roles of gathering and managing her household affairs and intersection of caste and class plays a role in this, because the experience of a high caste women will be different from the experiences and glorification of a working, real experience low class women. Women's participation in creating environmental protection in action is necessary because development is associated with control over the natural resources. Development in India is a concept that is accompanied with environmental ignorance creating a problematic situation.

Reference

- Agarwal B. The Gender and environment debate. *Feminist Stujdies*, 18(1):119-158.
- Agarwal, B. (2002). *Are we not peasants too*. SEEDS
- Carson, R. 1962. *Silent spring*
- Curzon. (1998). *Environmental movements in Asia*. United Kingdom: Curzon.
- Goswami, T. (2022). *Women Participation in Environmental Management: A Study*. Pacific.
- Griffin S. (1978) *Women and nature: The roaring inside her*. Harper and row.
- Omvedt, G. (2011). *Cultural revolt in a colonial society: The non-Brahman movement in western India*. India: Manohar Publications.
- Ortner, S. B. (1972). Is female to male as nature Is to culture? *Feminist Studies*, 1(2), 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3177638>
- Prasad, I. (2025). *Feminist and anti-caste activism in the Bodhgaya land movement of rural Bihar: "We achieved great feats!"*. Routledge. ISBN: 9781032578736
- Shiva, V., & Mies, M. (2014). *Ecofeminism*. Ireland, Zed Books.
- Suguna, B. (2009). *Women's movement*. India, Discovery Publishing House.